

To Study the Various Risk Factors Predisposing to Late Onset Septicemia in Neonates**Madhuchandan M¹, Megha P², Ganashree B³ & Udaykumar B⁴**^{1,2&3}Assistant Professor, Department of Pediatrics, Shridevi Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Hospital, Tumakuru - 572106, Karnataka, India⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Pediatrics, Sri Siddhartha Institute of Medical Sciences and Research centre, T Begur, Nelamangala - 562123, Karnataka, India

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Abstract:**Background & Methods:** The aim of the study is to study the various risk factors predisposing to late onset septicemia in neonates. A detailed maternal history was taken followed by examination of the neonate, the cases followed longitudinally regularly till discharge or death. The symptoms and signs were closely observed and recorded on case sheet as well as on proforma specially designed for the purpose.**Results:** The main clinical features in neonates with late onset septicemia were lethargy 89%, refusal to feed 84%, hypothermia 63%, jaundice 60%, mottling 42%, abdominal distension 30% while hyperthermia 22%, seizures 21%, bleeding & apneic episode 15%, bulging fontanelle were present only in 2% of the cases. Low birth weight (LBW) was associated with 90% cases followed by pre-maturity, RDS at birth, resuscitation at birth in decreasing order of frequency.**Conclusion:** Neonatal septicemia is more common in preterm, LBW and male babies. Peripheral intravenous cannula, IV fluids, LBW, pre-term, respiratory distress at birth increased duration of hospital stay are significant risk factors for late onset septicemia. Increased duration of hospital stay increases risk of sepsis and vice versa.**Keywords:** risk, predisposing, onset & septicemia.**Study Design:** Observational Study.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Late onset infection, the nursery incurred septicemia occurs usually after 72 hours of life. In late onset infection, the organism first colonize the baby and only later invade to cause sepsis [1]. Nosocomial septicemia was considered to be present if onset of infection was beyond 72 hours of life with positive culture of body fluids which are supposed to be sterile e.g. Blood, CSF, Urine [2]. Neonate who had clinical features suggestive of septicemia appearing after 72 hours of birth but not yielding bacterial pathogen on culture of body fluids were defined as having nosocomial septicemia if they had positive sepsis screen. Sepsis screen was considered to be positive if at least two tests out of five tests were positive. Components of sepsis screen includes abnormal leucocyte count (< 5000 - >20,000), absolute neutrophil count (low counts as per Manroe's or Mouzhino's chart), micro-ESR (>15 mm in 1st hour), C reactive Protein (CRP >1 mg/L) and immature to total neutrophil ratio (I/T ratio >0.2) [3].

Neonatal septicemia is still one of the major killers in the developing countries. Over 80% of neonatal deaths in hospital are caused by septicemia [4-6].

During the neonatal period the basic pattern of colonization is established and it is at this time the baby is most vulnerable to bacteria that do not harm the older children.

Material and Methods

A total of 200 newborns delivered & admitted were taken up for study. Newborn should be delivered & admitted for at least 72 hrs are included in study. Only those cases are selected who develops signs & symptoms after 72 hrs of birth.

A detailed maternal history was taken followed by examination of the neonate, the cases were followed longitudinally regularly till discharge or death. The symptoms and signs were closely observed and recorded on case sheet as well as on proforma specially designed for the purpose. The various symptoms that were inquired were fever, refusal of feed, loose motion, convulsions, respiratory distress, abdominal distension, vomiting, being dull.

The various clinical signs for looked for were weight, gestational age, hypothermia, crying,

activity, rooting, sucking, cyanosis, pallor, jaundice, and bleeding from any site.

Various risk factors predisposing to late onset sepsis were analyzed in detail for each baby e.g. birth weight, resuscitation at birth, gestational age, duration of stay, number of days for which peripheral vascular cannula was placed etc.

Exclusion criteria

1. Babies with PROM >12 hours
2. Maternal fever
3. Foul smelling liquor
4. Onset of symptoms within 72 hours of life

Result

Table 1: Showing Distribution of Cases According to Weight

S. No.	Weight in Kg.	No. of Cases (200)	Percentage
1.	<1.49	100	50%
2.	1.5 - 1.99	56	28%
3.	2.00 - 2.49	28	14%
4.	> 2.50	16	8%

The above table shows that majority of clinically septic case were 1-2 Kg weight group 78% of total. The total number of LBW babies below 2.5 kgs. shown in table as 92% of total cases.

Table 2: Showing the Distribution of Cases According to Mode of Delivery

S. No.	Mode of Delivery	No. of Cases (200)	Percentage
1.	NVD	142	71%
2.	LSCS	58	29%

Above table shows that 71% babies were normal vaginal delivered.

Table 3: Clinical Features of Neonatal Septicemia

S. No.	Clinical Features	No. of Cases(200)	Percentage
1.	Lethargy	178	89%
2.	Refusal to feed	168	84%
3.	Hypothermia	126	63%
4.	Jaundice	120	60%
5.	Gastric residual	92	46%
6.	Mottling	84	42%
7.	Generalized pallor	74	37%
8.	Abdominal distension	60	30%
9.	Hyperthermia	44	22%
10.	Seizure episodes	42	21%
11.	Sclerema	38	19%
12.	Bleeding IV/GI/other	30	15%
13.	Apneic episode	30	15%
14.	Bulging fontanelle	04	2%

The main clinical features as shown in above table were lethargy 89%, refusal to feed 84% jaundice 60%, hypothermia 63%, mottling 42%, abdominal distension 30% while hyperthermia 22%, seizures 21%, bleeding & apneic episode 15%, bulging fontanelle were present only in 2% of the cases.

Table 4: Showing the Distribution of Cases According to Neonatal Risk Factors

S. No.	Risk Factor	No. of Cases (200)	Percentage
1.	LBW	180	90%
2.	Pre-term	154	77%
3.	RDS at birth	70	35%
4.	Resuscitation at birth	52	26%
5.	Hyperbilirubinemia	02	1%
6.	Male sex	128	64%

Above table shows that low birth weight was associated with 90% cases followed by pre-maturity, male sex, RDS at birth, resuscitation at birth in decreasing order of frequency.

Discussion

From the findings of this study, neonatal sepsis is common and contributes significantly to mortality

among neonates admitted in the neonatal ward at a tertiary care hospital in Tumakuru. The prevalence of positive blood culture sepsis of 22.4% observed in this study is higher than 15.9% reported by Bloomberg et al. [7]. It is also higher than 6.5% which was reported by Klingenberg et al. [8] from a study conducted in another Tanzanian referral hospital.

The increase in prevalence of sepsis could be accounted for by the increase in resistance to antimicrobials which may have resulted in inadequate treatment in lower health care facilities. Collectively, our study and that of Bloomberg et al. [7] indicate a high magnitude of neonatal sepsis in developing countries, which may reflect suboptimal quality of advanced neonatal care as opposed to developed countries which have lower prevalence rates of neonatal sepsis.

In this study, the overall neonatal mortality was 13.9%, being higher in neonates with sepsis (24%) as compared to those without (10%). Reports from other two referral hospitals in Tanzania by Kayange et al. [9] and Klingenberg et al. [8] found infant mortality due to neonatal sepsis to be 19% and matched closely with the findings of 18% by Mugalu et al. in a Ugandan study. Collectively, these findings reflect the significant contribution of neonatal sepsis in both neonatal and infant mortality.

Gestational age not only affects weight of the baby but also predisposes babies to increased risk of sepsis. In the present study, 73% babies were pre-terms, while only 27% were term, these observations were supported by different authors. Anil Kumar Pawa et al reported 33.5 wk gestation with infected groups, and 36.6 wk in non-infected group, a lower gestational age increases risk of septicaemia[10].

The clinical features of neonatal sepsis are nonspecific and vague. In this study most common findings were refusal to feed (93%) and lethargy (89%). Incidence of jaundice was reported by other workers however jaundice developing in neonate is confounding factor as in significant - proportion of cases it is physiological and in some cases it may be due to sepsis per se[11-13]. In the present study jaundice was detected in 63% of cases but-in 77.7% cases jaundice appears to be physiological while 16.67% cases were outside the physiological range, and 31% cases of jaundice were of direct hyperbilirubinemia.

Conclusion

Neonatal septicemia is more common in preterm, LBW and male babies. Peripheral intravenous cannula, IV fluids, LBW, pre-term, respiratory distress at birth increased duration of hospital stay are significant risk factors for late onset septicemia.

Increased duration of hospital stay increases risk of sepsis and vice versa.

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